

SCHOOL PRINCIPAL MANAGEMENT IN IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract

School principals have a significant role in creating an environment that supports teacher professional development. His performance is not only responsible for school administration but also acts as a leader who provides direction, support and necessary resources to teachers to continue to improve their professional competence. The aim of the research is to analyze the planning, implementation and follow-up of Deming's theory. Results and conclusions research The principal has carried out a series of efforts to improve teachers' professional competence by carrying out an intense coaching process in meetings, evaluations, official meetings, class meetings and post-class observations, involving teachers in various training, workshop seminars and activating KKG as a forum for collaboration. Teacher.

Keywords: Management, Principal, Professional, and Elementary School Teacher.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the main pillar in the development of a nation and teachers have a very important role in ensuring quality education. Professionally competent teachers have a significant impact on students' intellectual, social and emotional development. Education is also a sector that continues to develop, where rapid changes in educational paradigms require intensive adaptation from educators. The emphasis on student-centered education, learning models and methods and technology, and the changing needs of the job market, emphasize the need to increase teacher professional competence. Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System (UU Sisdiknas), mandates changes in the education process in Indonesia to produce Human Resources (HR) that are relevant to the situation, conditions and needs of society. This mandate is stated in the Independent Curriculum policy. Teachers are required to have the requirements and criteria desired by the world of education. One of the requirements that teachers must have is academic qualifications that are appropriate to their field as stated in Law Number 14 of 2005 concerning teachers and lecturers. Article 8 states that "Teachers are required to have academic qualifications, educational competence, be physically and spiritually healthy, and have the ability to realize national education goals and in article 10 paragraph (1) states that:

"Teacher competence as referred to in Article 8 includes pedagogical competence, personality competence, social competence and professional competence obtained through professional education."

Teacher professionalism refers to a series of attitudes, behaviors and skills that reflect commitment and integrity in carrying out their duties and responsibilities as educators. This

professionalism is implemented in a high level of performance and discipline, apart from that, a manifestation of professionalism is the ability to educate, teach and train students in the learning process and produce quality output (graduates). School principals have a significant role in creating an environment that supports teacher professional development. They are not only responsible for school administration but also act as leaders who provide direction, support and necessary resources to teachers to continuously improve their professional competence. The role of school principals in improving teachers' professional competence is a key element in improving the quality of education.

This is proven that not all teachers who have educational certificates show a level of professionalism in the learning process or a low level of discipline and feel comfortable with the current conditions or circumstances so that learning activities tend to be monotonous and boring for students and in the end learning that is in favor of students is not can be realized optimally. Another problem related to internal teacher factors is the low motivation of teachers in efforts to improve their professional abilities. Another internal factor is the lack of motivation that comes from within him to improve his competence, even though the curriculum and learning models continue to develop. Very little of the professional allowances obtained are used for professional development but rather for consumerism for personal needs. This condition will certainly hinder efforts to improve teachers' professional abilities. With the educator certification program, teachers should have better professional skills in teaching activities. The problems above are interesting to research, so the following research title emerged: "School Principal Management in Improving the Professional Competence of Elementary School Teachers (Case Study at SDN 2 Sukakarya Samarang, Garut Regency and SDIT Bina Muda Cicalengka, Bandung Regency)".

SDN 2 Sukakarya Samarang and SDIT Bina Muda Cicalengka were taken as research objects because SDIT Bina Muda Cicalengka is one of the favorite elementary schools in Cicalengka District in particular and the East Bandung area in general with a high level of discipline, SDIT Bina Muda Cicalengka is also one of the driving schools. SDN 2 Sukakarya Samarang, Garut Regency was chosen as the research object because SDN 2 Sukakarya is the elementary school in Samarang sub-district which has the most active teachers. Principals at both schools have taken various efforts to develop teachers' professional abilities in developing quality through various training, comparative studies, supervision and guidance from the education department, so that it can be seen that the implementation of principal management in improving teacher professionalism

RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in this research is analytical descriptive with a naturalistic qualitative approach. According to Sugiyono (2018) qualitative research methods are research methods used to research the conditions of natural objects, where the researcher is the key instrument, data collection techniques are carried out in a triangulated (combined) manner, data analysis is inductive, and qualitative research results emphasize meaning. Rather than generalizations. Through this research, the author attempts to describe and analyze school principal

management patterns in improving the professional competence of elementary school teachers. According to William Edwards Deming (1986: 9) states that management functions include; Plan (Plan), Do (Do), Check (Check/Evaluate), and Act (Action).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Principal planning in improving the professional competence of elementary school teachers

The principal's planning to increase the professionalism of teachers in elementary schools is a crucial step to ensure the quality of education. Some of the strategies used are:

Providing motivation for teachers to understand their role and function as educators and instructors so that learning is more meaningful. This motivation is provided in the form of moral support, appreciation for the performance and good practices carried out by teachers and encouraging teachers to continue to innovate and develop themselves. Apart from that, it provides training (workshops) both in internal and external environments which aim to improve the skills of teachers. This training includes learning models, technology and curriculum development. Carrying out regular academic supervision/class supervision activities. With regular supervision activities, the school principal can directly observe what is the process of learning activities carried out by teachers in class, from the results of academic supervision/class supervision, the principal provides constructive feedback for subsequent learning activities. Class meetings are held once a week with the aim of evaluating the implementation of teaching and learning activities for one week and the problems that arise. faced by the teacher and the steps taken by the teacher, so that solutions to problems that occur can be quickly taken. With a participative leadership style, where the principal involves teachers in the decision-making process so that teachers feel recognized for their existence and can become decision makers when there are problems. Activating Teacher Working Groups (KKG), as a forum for collaboration and exchanging ideas for teachers regarding learning models and learning programs that support students. The school principal facilitates regular KKG meetings to improve teacher competency. Teacher Evaluation Meeting which aims to carry out routine evaluations of teacher performance. This evaluation can help identify teacher strengths and weaknesses and provide recommendations for improvement. Finally, hold visits to other schools (comparative studies) or invite teachers from other schools to share experiences and best practices

2. Implementation of school principals in improving the professional competence of elementary school teachers

Implementation is the implementation of program planning or activities that have been prepared by the school principal to improve teacher professional competence. This implementation is an important aspect to ensure the quality of education. The implementation of this activity program includes the following:

- a. Conduct evaluation meetings on learning activities and implementation of school programs 3x in one school year (The beginning of the school year is for planning

activity programs that will be implemented during one school year. The beginning of the even semester is an evaluation of odd semester activities, and the end of the even semester is an evaluation of even semester teaching and learning activities)

- b. Carry out academic supervision/class supervision 2x every school year. The odd semester is held in September-October while the even semester is held in February-March.
- c. The meeting class as a weekly evaluation is held every week, namely on Wednesdays from 13.00 – 15.00.
- d. Sending teachers to various training activities, be it training related to subjects or other academic activities, (upgrading/in-service training), workshops and seminars to improve teachers' abilities.
- e. Optimizing the role and function of the KKG as a forum for collaboration on learning models and good practices in order to improve teacher competence.
- f. Create an Annual School Work Plan (RKTS) which includes 8 educational standards as a guideline for improving teacher competency.
- g. Establish good communication with all stakeholders in the school to create a productive work climate and work culture.
- h. Conduct comparative studies of schools that are considered good in implementing school programs that support students as a reference for creating programs in schools.

3. Evaluation of school principals in improving the professional competence of elementary school teachers.

As part of quality management, evaluation of teacher performance is very necessary for school principals to improve teacher professional competence. An important evaluation is to ensure the quality of education. Some of the evaluations carried out include the following:

- a. Teacher Performance Assessment (PK Guru): School principals can carry out regular performance assessments of teachers. Teacher PK covers aspects of professional competence, pedagogy and personality.
- b. The principal carries out direct supervision of the learning process in the classroom. By observing and providing feedback, school principals can help teachers improve their competence.
- c. Hold discussion forums with teachers to discuss experiences, challenges and solutions in teaching as well as good practices that have been implemented by teachers. This discussion forum activity allows school principals to understand the needs of teachers and provide appropriate support.
- d. School principals can ensure teachers participate in regular training and professional development. This includes workshops, seminars and training related to curriculum and learning methods.

- e. The school principal evaluates teacher effectiveness based on exam result data, learning evaluations and student performance. This evaluation will help the school principal identify areas that need to be improved, maintained and improved.
- f. The principal collaborates with teachers in planning corrective actions. Teachers can provide input about training needs or necessary support.
- g. Rewards and Development: The principal gives awards for teacher achievements and efforts in improving competence. In addition, school principals can identify further development opportunities

4. The principal's actions in improving the professional competence of elementary school teachers

The principal's actions in improving the professional competence of primary school teachers are an important aspect of ensuring the quality of education. This action is carried out based on the results of the evaluation carried out by the principal on teacher performance. The actions taken by the principal to improve teacher professionalism include:

- a. Based on the results of the Class Supervision evaluation that has been carried out, the principal carries out follow-up actions on teachers who are deemed to need to improve both pedagogical competence and professional competence by carrying out clinical supervision. Clinical supervision is carried out based on post-observation activities with coaching carried out by the school principal for the teacher concerned. By observing and providing constructive feedback, from the results of classroom observations the principal can help teachers improve their competence.
- b. Regarding the problems and obstacles faced by teachers, both in the learning process and other activities, the school principal holds discussion forums, both in official meetings and during class meetings, with the hope that teachers will openly express their concerns and what teachers need to improve the quality of learning. in the classroom.
- c. To increase teacher competence in developing learning models, learning methods and developing curriculum and programs that have an impact on students, school principals motivate and involve teachers in various training workshops, seminars, etc.
- d. The principal collaborates with teachers in designing activities/programs and planning corrective actions. Teachers can provide input about training needs or necessary support.
- e. Giving Awards and Development: The principal gives awards for teacher achievements and efforts in improving competence. In addition, school principals can identify further development opportunities.

5. Obstacles faced by school principals in improving teacher professional competence.

Obstacles faced by school principals in improving teacher professional competence include:

- a. It is difficult to change the mindset of teachers who do not want to get out of their comfort zone, resulting in learning activities that are still teacher centric.
- b. Lack of enthusiasm for teachers to take part in training activities or seminars to improve their competence and abilities and lack of intrinsic motivation from within the teachers themselves.
- c. There is an unequal workload resulting in a gap between teachers, so that some teachers are more active in participating in training or supporting activities, while others may participate less.
- d. The conflict between support activities and routine working hours can be an obstacle. Teachers who have a full teaching load may find it difficult to attend training or seminars outside of working hours.
- e. The school's budget is limited, where more of the budget is allocated for physical school facilities and infrastructure activities, while the percentage for program activities is very small, thus having an impact on the quality of learning.
- f. There is a lack of self-confidence in teachers to reveal their shortcomings which results in communication not being effective.

6. Solutions for elementary school principals in improving the professional competence of elementary school teachers

Regarding the obstacles faced by school principals in improving teachers' professional competence, the solutions taken are as follows:

a. Ongoing Training and Development:

- 1) Hold regular training for teachers, including in preparing Teaching Modules, Learning Goal Flow, Learning Objectives, Learning Outcomes and Learning Goal Achievement Criteria (KKTP).
- 2) Activate Teacher Working Groups (KKG) to share experiences and knowledge as well as learning models.
- 3) Improving teacher qualifications through training and further education.
- 4) Use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT):
- 5) Utilize ICT for communication and self-development.
- 6) Using technology in the learning and evaluation process.

b. Improvement of Teacher Qualifications:

Ensure teachers have qualifications that are appropriate to their duties and responsibilities. Encourage teachers to take part in certification and training programs.

c. Cooperation and Collaboration:

Building collaboration between teachers, principals and deputy principals.
Encourage collaboration in curriculum development and learning methods.

d. School Resource Management:

Ensure the availability of adequate facilities and infrastructure for learning.
Optimize the use of funds and other resources.
Make a balanced budget for the development of physical facilities and infrastructure with school development programs.
Making program plans based on assets, not based on needs

e. Monitoring and Evaluation:

Conduct regular teacher performance evaluations.
Provide constructive feedback for improvement.
Building effective communication with teachers and involving teachers in the decision-making process (participative leadership style)

CONCLUSION

The school principal has carried out a series of efforts to improve teachers' professional competence by carrying out an intense coaching process in meetings, evaluations, official meetings, class meetings and post-class observations, involving teachers in various training, workshop seminars and activating KKG as a forum for teacher collaboration. The obstacles or constraints faced by school principals in improving teachers' professional competence, the main obstacles come from teachers, namely not wanting to leave their comfort zone and the limited budget for teacher development and school programs.

- 1) Principal planning in improving the professional competence of elementary school teachers.

In an effort to improve teachers' professional competence, the plans made include an intense coaching process in meetings, evaluations, official meetings, class meetings and post-class observations, involving teachers in various training, workshop seminars and activating KKG as a forum for teacher collaboration.

- 2) Implementation of school principals in improving the professional competence of elementary school teachers.

Implementation of activities to improve teacher professional competence is by conducting class supervision, class meetings and regular evaluation meetings, as well as involving teachers in various training activities, including seminars, training (workshops) as well as activating and facilitating KKG.

- 3) Evaluation of school principals in improving the professional competence of elementary school teachers.

Evaluation is carried out upon completion of the implementation of the program/activity held at the meeting or class meeting

- 4) The principal's actions in improving the professional competence of elementary school teachers.

Actions taken to improve teachers' professional competence as a result of evaluation activities include the school principal carrying out clinical supervision of teachers whose performance is deemed to need to be improved and improved as well as giving awards and appreciation to teachers who have a good work ethic.

- 5) Obstacles faced by school principals in improving teacher professional competence,

The main obstacles are the difficulty of changing the mindset of teachers who do not want to leave their comfort zone and limited budgets for development and training programs as well as communication that does not run effectively.

- 6) Solutions for elementary school principals in improving the professional competence of elementary school teachers.

The solution to the obstacles faced is for schools to hold training and send teachers to various trainings and involve teachers in preparing programs/activities using (participatory management).

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